

A First Look at the Circumstellar Dust Composition of M-type Mira Variables observed with Spitzer

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Abstract

Our research is on the dust composition surrounding Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) stars. In particular, the AGB star sub-group called Mira variables. These regular pulsators are easily observed in the optical and infrared due to their changes in brightness. Data on 25 Galactic Miras were obtained with the IRS instrument on Spitzer Space Telescope in 2008-09. The stars were observed once per month to monitor changes in their brightness and spectral features. This dataset is unique, not only for the number of observations of each star, but also because of the high signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) due to the intrinsic brightness of the targets. By taking quick exposure times while sampling the data, the saturation of the detectors was avoided.

The current focus of our research is on the high resolution data observed in the mid-infrared wavelength range ($\sim 9 - 40$ microns). The reduced spectra reveal a wonderful forest of features which provide insight into the stellar atmosphere and circumstellar dust composition. The stars in our sample can be categorized into either oxygen- or carbon-rich stars, with each type exhibiting certain known solid state components (i.e. dust). Preliminary study of the oxygen-rich dust composition shows the primary known features, such as broad silicate emission and aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3). Additional broad, and some sharp, dust features are currently being identified using the radiative transfer modeling code, DUSTY, along with recently derived laboratory spectral indexes for dust. Initial identifications of prominent dust features seen in oxygen-rich Miras include potential contributions from water emission, as well as crystalline and amorphous silicates, and possibly corundum. Preliminary results for a sub-sample of the set is presented here.

1 Introduction

Asymptotic Giant Branch (AGB) stars are low to intermediate mass stars ($0.8 - 8 M_{\odot}$) in the final stages of their evolution and have mass loss rates as high as $10^{-4} M_{\odot}/yr$. Hydrogen and helium burning shells sit atop the carbon and oxygen ash core. Thermodynamical instabilities in the shell burning layer cause yearly atmospheric pulses. AGB stars with regular pulsations of about 200 - 500 days are called Mira variables, and are easily identified in both optical and infrared due to their regular changes in brightness. Using C/O ratio, Mira variables are classified into three chemical subclasses: M, S, and C (i.e. $C/O < 1$, $C/O \sim 1$, and $C/O > 1$, respectively).

1.1 Spitzer Space Telescope Data

High and low resolution data for 25 Galactic Miras were acquired during 2008-09 with the Infrared Spectrograph (IRS) instrument (Houck *et al.*, 2004) on the Spitzer Space Telescope under a GO program led by Creech-Eakman (Creech-Eakman *et al.*, 2008). These Miras were selected because they are primarily within the Galactic plane (~ 1 kpc), have optically thin dust emission, and cover all three chemical subclasses. The IRS instrument has four different modules to allow for detailed infrared observations. The stars were observed approximately once per month and the changes in their brightness were monitored. The number of observations obtained for these Miras allows us to study their composition and look for phase dependent behavior in the dust. Infrared observations of such bright stars would normally saturate the detectors and make the data unusable, however this was avoided by using short exposure times during observations. The current focus of the research is on the short, high (SH) and long, high (LH) resolution wavelength range (~ 9.7 to 40 microns) because they were least likely to saturate the detectors but still provide high SNR observations.

Figure 1: Illustration of *complex Mira atmosphere* showing features of carbon, oxygen, and mixed chemistry (<https://www.asiaa.sinica.edu.tw/research/icsm.php>)

These AGB stars can be categorized into either oxygen- or carbon-rich stars, with each type exhibiting certain known solid state components (i.e. dust) as previously identified using for example IRAS Low Resolution Spectrometer (LRS) and ISO Long Wavelength Spectrometer (LWS) (cf. Little-Marenin & Little (1990); Tsuji *et al.* (1997)). Prelimi-

nary study of the oxygen-rich dust composition shows the presence of primary known features, such as broad silicate emission and aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3).

2 Data Reduction and Modeling Process

The high resolution data reduction is based on recipes provided in the Spitzer Data Analysis Cookbook¹, published by the Spitzer Space Telescope. The data were obtained during the last cycle of the cryogenic phase component of the Spitzer telescope. Though these Galactic Mira variables are very bright in the infrared, it was recommended by the Spitzer Space Telescope team to obtain dedicated sky backgrounds for each observation due to the low cryogen levels and potential problems affiliated with the end of the cryogenic mission. Each pointing also included a peak-up on a nearby target.

The first step in the reduction process was the subtraction of the dedicated sky background from the data instead of the more common approach of nod-nod subtraction. The next step was the removal of any random bad/rogue pixels using *IRSCLEAN* tool from Spitzer. The extraction of the spectrum and flux uncertainties were accomplished using the *SPICE* tool. Note that the flux uncertainties for the individual nods of each star were median combined. Due to the brightness of these stars, the spectrum was defringed using *IRSFINGE*, followed by the order overlap removal according to the IRS Data Reduction Cookbook. Lastly, the individual nods were combined, using our own IDL codes and IRAF programs, to create the final spectrum. For more details on the reduction process see Creech-Eakman *et al.* (2012).

2.1 DUSTY

DUSTY is 1-D radiative transfer modeling code published by Ivezić *et al.* (1999). The user provides the stellar and circumstellar dust properties in DUSTY to obtain a dust dependent spectrum. Variations in the input parameters, which include inner dust shell temperature, optical depth, dust density, and grain size distribution, are plentiful and require user discretion depending on the chemical subclass. The first step in using DUSTY is to set a star temperature in the input parameters to obtain a theoretical blackbody radiation curve. For now, we are using 2900K for M-type stars from which DUSTY then calculates the scattering and absorption of a given grain distribution. We will use DUSTY to determine the well-known dust features generally found in these chemical subclasses, and incorporate appropriate optical constants for chemical species that are not included in the DUSTY libraries. This will allow us to determine particular dust chemistries and how they change over the course of the pulsation cycle.

3 Spitzer IRS High Resolution Spectra

Figure 2 is one example of a high resolution reduced spectrum. *S Psc* (HD 7773) is a M-type Mira variable (Keenan, 1966) and only had two observations taken during the program mission. It has a period of approximately 404 days (Sloan & Price, 1998) and an angular diameter of 3.84 milliarcseconds at a phase of 0.92 as measured by Ridgway *et al.* (1979). This star was observed using IRAS SWS and LWS, and found to have significant dust emission

Figure 2: High resolution spectra of *S Psc*, an oxygen rich Mira variable. The median combined flux uncertainty is provided. Note that it is given as 3σ RMS due to its low 1σ median value. The top and bottom panels are at phase 0.990 and 0.042, respectively.

features in the mid-infrared (Onaka *et al.*, 1989). No masers (SiO , H_2O , or OH) have currently been detected in *S Psc* (Bowers & Sinha, 1978; Bowers & Hagen, 1984; Vardya, 1987; Sivagnanam *et al.*, 1988; Lewis, 1997).

This M-type Mira displays characteristics of some well known solid state emission features, such as the amorphous silicate at ~ 10 micron and aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3), and several distinct emission spectral features. Those spectral features are being investigated by Dana Baylis-Aguirre (New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology) and a sample of her research is presented in these conference proceedings.

4 Preliminary Abundances from DUSTY

Here we present an example output of the dust abundances obtained from DUSTY for O-rich AGB star *S Psc*. The primary dust features are labeled in Figure 3. The Spitzer data was normalized and scaled to make it more readable when plotted on the same grid as the DUSTY output. It should be noted that the DUSTY output is not well-aligned with the Spitzer data, which will require a graybody or more sophisticated approach instead of a blackbody. Several strong dust emission features are present in *S Psc*; in particular warm and cold silicates, compact Al_2O_3 , and iron(II) oxide or wüstite (FeO). See Table 1 for the complete list of dust grain abundances.

Table 1: Relative Dust Abundances

Star Name	<i>S Psc</i>	References
Warm Silicate	0.2	Ossenkopf <i>et al.</i> (1992)
Cold Silicate	0.1	Ossenkopf <i>et al.</i> (1992)
Ice (-7°C)	0.1	Warren (1984)
FeO	0.3	Henning <i>et al.</i> (1995)
Glassy Olivine	0.1	Dorschner <i>et al.</i> (1995)
Comp Al_2O_3	0.2	Begemann <i>et al.</i> (1997)

¹<http://irsa.ipac.caltech.edu/data/SPITZER/docs/dataanalysis/tools/cookbook/home/>

Figure 3: Sample output for *S Psc* 2008-08-12

5 Discussions

An example of one of the M-type AGB stars from our dataset is provided. Using DUSTY, a preliminary identification of some broad dust features was conducted for *S Psc* and presented here. Besides the well known broad features, we also want to scrutinize unidentified, smaller dust features to develop a best-fit scenario to determine more detailed dust compositions of this dataset. For more details on the dataset, refer to Creech-Eakman *et al.* (2012). DUSTY is a complex and extensive radiative transfer code that will allow us to expand on the input parameters and create several variations. More detailed and refined dust abundances for these AGB stars require that we obtain more optical constant tables that are compatible with DUSTY. Making progress with the dust compositions of oxygen-rich AGB stars, will allow us to expand into determining the dust mixtures for the carbon-rich Mira variables.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

We have started to investigate the broad dust features in several oxygen rich Mira variables from our dataset. However, as seen in Figure 3, the DUSTY output does not match well with the Spitzer data, particularly in the continuum levels. In discussions with Dr. Bernhard Aringer (University of Padova/STARKEY), a graybody continuum should overcome this problem. In particular, the MARCS code has been suggested by both Dr. Aringer and Dr. Claudia Paladini (Université Libre de Bruxelles) during the conference. We are currently in the process of implementing those recommendations, along with gathering more optical constant tables from the community, so that we can investigate circumstellar dust composition of other O-rich AGB stars from our sample. In that regard, we have obtained data from the Palomar Testbed Interferometer (PTI), which is part of a larger multi-wavelength observational AGB campaign, to constrain some of the dust continuum parameters, such as temperature and bolometric flux. Not only will this allow for the detailed dust composition of O-rich AGB stars, but also contribute to determining if there are any correlations between the oxygen- and carbon-rich Mira variables and dust production with phase.

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